

**Cyclisation of 2-Acetylamino-cinnamanilides
in Presence of Aromatic Aldehydes. One-pot
Synthesis of 1-Aryl-4-benzylidene-2-
styryl-2-imidazolin-5-ones**

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ACETIC acid mediated cyclisation of 2-acetylamino-cinnamanilides (**1a**) to the corresponding 2-methyl-imidazolin-5-ones (**2**) was reported to be unsuccessful¹. In order to verify the Baldwin rule², we reinvestigated this reaction and have found that **2** ($Ar^1=Ph$) is indeed formed but it decomposes on heating. With a view to converting the thermally unstable compound **2**, generated *in situ*, into a more stable system, we have now carried out the cyclisation of **1a** in the presence of suitable aromatic aldehydes and have found the products to be 2-styryl-2-imidazolin-5-ones (**3**). The formation of the products **3** is obviously due to the condensation of the activated methyl group of **2** with the aromatic aldehyde present in the reaction mixture. Synthesis of **3** by the cyclocondensation of **1b** is possible, but

this would involve several steps, starting from the preparation of cinnamoylglycine. This procedure would be difficult to apply in the case of **3** carrying a free hydroxyl group, for example **3b**. Also, the conversion of **1** by the reported method^{3,4} requires very long time and the use of Schiff bases^{5,6} for obtaining **3** involves additional step. The present one-pot synthesis overcomes these difficulties. The starting materials are easily available and the reaction is quite fast. The products were characterised by spectral data and elemental analyses. The alternative structure **4** is ruled out on the basis of ¹H nmr spectra in which the signal for a methyl group is not discernible and two doublets near the aro-

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL, ANALYTICAL, AND ¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF 4-BENZYLIDENE-2-STYRYL-2-IMIDAZOLIN-5-ONES (**3**)

Compd. no.	Ar ¹	Ar ²	Yield %	M p. °C	δ (ppm)*	Molecular formula	Analysis % · Found/(Calcd.)		
							O	H	N
3a	Ph	Ph	61	240	6.46(1H, d, J 14 Hz, PhOH=OH), 7.06–7.53(14H, m, ArH and 4-C=OH), 7.94(1H, d, J 14 Hz, PhOH=CH), 8.06–8.28(2H, m, Ar-H).	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ H ₂ O	78.19 (78.26)	5.60 (5.43)	7.72 (7.60)
3b	Ph	2-HO-C ₆ H ₄	41	244	Insufficiently soluble	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃ H ₂ O	74.85 (75.00)	4.89 (5.20)	7.49 (7.28)
3c	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	Ph	66	213–14	6.43(1H, d, J 14 Hz, PhOH=OH), 7.06–7.62(18H, m, ArH and 4-C=OH), 7.93(1H, d, J 14 Hz, PhOH=CH), 8.06–8.32(2H, m, Ar-H).	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ OCl	74.92 (74.90)	4.72 (4.42)	6.95 (7.27)
3d	4-MeO-C ₆ H ₄	Ph	69	195	3.83(3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.48(1H, d, J 14 Hz, PhOH=OH), 6.87–7.48(13H, m, ArH and 4-C=OH), 7.93(1H, d, J 14 Hz, PhOH=CH), 8.09–8.28(2H, m, ArH).	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃ .1/2H ₂ O	77.42 (77.23)	5.52 (5.39)	6.90 (7.19)
3e	4-Me-C ₆ H ₄	Ph	55	186–87	2.44(3H, s, ArCH ₃), 6.53(1H, d, J 14 Hz, PhOH=OH), 7.03–7.53(18H, m, ArH and 4-C=OH), 7.97(1H, d, J 14 Hz, PhOH=CH), 8.39–8.94(2H, m, ArH).	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O.1/2H ₂ O	80.72 (80.46)	5.33 (5.63)	7.71 (7.60)

* (CDCl₃/TMS).

matic region with coupling constants of 14 Hz (Table 1) accounts for the (*Z*)-configuration of the styryl moiety. The anilides (1a) used were the authentic (*Z*)-isomers which would cyclise to the corresponding (*Z*)-4-benzylidene-2-methyl-2-imidazol-5-one (2) which in turn would react with the aldehydes to give 3. It should be emphasised that on steric consideration the (*Z*)-compound 2 is more stable than its (*E*)-isomer and there is no question of its undergoing isomerisation during heating. Thus, the configuration of the olefinic centre at 4-position of 3 is (*Z*).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. ^1H nmr spectra were recorded on a JEOL 90Q spectrophotometer.

1-Aryl-4-benzylidene-2-styryl-2-imidazol-5-ones (3). *General procedure*: A mixture of 2-acetylaminocinnamamide⁷ (1a; 1.0 mol) and aromatic aldehyde (5; 1.1 mol) was heated under reflux in glacial acetic acid (15 ml/g of the anilide) for 2 h, using freshly fused sodium acetate as a catalyst. After the usual work-up the product was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid. Physical data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

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Synthesis of New Thiazolidinone Derivatives as Biologically Active Agents

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THIAZOLIDINONES are potential antibacterial¹, antifungal^{2,3} and insecticidal⁴ agents. 1,3,4-Thiadiazole derivatives have been reported to act as antibacterial⁵, antifungal⁶, insecticidal⁷ and herbici-

dal⁸ agents. Thus keeping the above conjecture in mind, a series of 2-[(5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)imino]-3-(4-substituted-phenyl)thiazolid-4-ones (4a-o) and their arylidene derivatives (5a-o) were synthesised.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 177 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Varian EM-360 spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as internal reference. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel-G plates and visualised by iodine vapour.

2-Amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (1a-c): The compounds were prepared by the reported method⁹.

Phenyl isothiocyanates (2): The compounds were obtained by reported method¹⁰.